

Synthesis and microbial activity of acrylamides with heteroatoms

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Abstract : The modified condensation reaction of benzaldehyde (1a), 2-chlorobenzaldehyde (1c), 3-nitrobenzaldehyde (1b) and 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (1d) with α -proton containing acids viz. acetic acid (2a) and similar reaction of propionic acid (2b) with 3-nitrobenzaldehyde (1b) and 4-chlorobenzaldehyde (1d) in the presence of sodium borohydride to afford corresponding acrylic acids (3a-f) which on further reaction with amines like morpholine (4) and 4-aminophenazone (5) in the presence of base and thionylchloride yielded series of acrylamides (6a-f and 7a-f). Physical data (yield, melting point, state and colour) of synthesized acids and amides were determined. The synthesized acrylamides and α,β -unsaturated acids were characterized by IR and ¹H NMR spectroscopy. Amide derivative were tested for their microbial activity on *Rhizobium* sp. (LMR 07), *Bradyrhizobium* sp. (BJP), *Pseudomonas* sp. (LK 791) and *Bacillus* sp. (BSY 101) at different concentration. Amides with morpholine moiety showed promising results.

Keywords : α,β -Unstaturated acid, amide, IR, NMR, *Rhizobium*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, microbial activity.

Introduction

Amide functionality plays an important role in the biological system for example in joining different amino acids to form proteins. Amide linkages are not limited to biological system instead they are present in large number of molecules including drugs¹. Medicinal chemistry database revealed that carboxamide group appear in more than 25% of known drugs². In the past decades, the problem of multidrug resistant microorganisms has reached on alarming level around the world³ and the synthesis of new antiinfective compounds has become an urgent need for the treatment of microbial infections.

Microbial agents based on a heterocyclic molecular structure have been used empirically and purposefully for a considerable time. Exploitation of heterocyclic chemical group has become more aggressive recently as a result of the limitations placed on the use of phenolic and mercury containing compounds by regulatory agencies. During the past few decades many results have been pub-

lished in the area of synthesis and the study of physical and chemical properties of heterocyclic compounds. Substituted heterocyclic compounds are ubiquitous structural units in natural products and pharmaceuticals³ and have been widely used as synthetic intermediates^{4,5}.

Variously substituted pyrazolines and their derivatives have played a crucial part in the development of theory in heterocyclic chemistry and also been used extensively as useful synthons in organic synthesis⁶. Morpholine compounds are class of compounds well known for a long time, mainly due to their application in different fields. The primary use of morpholine is an intermediate in the manufacture of pharmaceuticals particularly⁷.

Therefore, it was thought to investigate the synthesis of carboxamide derivatives by condensing acrylic acid derivatives (synthesized by condensation reaction of benzaldehyde and α -proton carrying acids) with different amines. The structures of these compounds were assigned on the basis of IR and ¹H NMR spectral data.

Results and discussion

In the present work an attempt has been made to synthesize acrylamide derivatives of some α,β -carboxylic acids. The condensation reaction of substituted benzaldehyde with either of acetic acid or propionic acid in the presence of sodium borohydride (Scheme 1) yielded α,β unsaturated acids, viz. *E*-3-phenylacrylic acid (**3a**), *E*-3-(3-nitrophenyl)acrylic acid (**3b**), *E*-3-(2-chlorophenyl)acrylic acid (**3c**), *E*-3-(4-chlorophenyl)acrylic acid (**3d**), *E*-2-methyl-3-(3-nitrophenyl)acrylic acid (**3e**) and *E*-2-methyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)acrylic acid (**3f**) which upon further condensation with different amines (morpholine, 4-aminophenazone) in the presence of triethylamine and thionyl chloride with constant stirring for half an hour at 0 °C and for further 2 h at room temperature gave respective amides *E*-1-morpholino-3-(phenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6a**), *E*-*N*-(1,5-dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-3-(phenyl)acrylamide (**7a**), *E*-1-morpholino-3-(3-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6b**), *E*-*N*-(1,5-dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-3-(3-nitrophenyl)acrylamide (**7b**), *E*-1-morpholino-3-(2-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6c**), *E*-*N*-(1,5-dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-3-(2-chlorophenyl)acrylamide (**7c**), *E*-1-morpholino-3-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6d**), *E*-*N*-(1,5-dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)acrylamide (**7d**), *E*-2-methyl-1-morpholino-3-(3-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6e**), *E*-*N*-(1,5-dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-2-methyl-3-(3-nitrophenyl)acrylamide (**7e**), *E*-2-methyl-1-morpholino-3-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6f**) and *E*-*N*-(1,5-dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-2-methyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)acrylamide (**7f**) (Scheme 2). Physical data (yield, melting point, state and colour) of acids and amides are given in Table 1. IR and ¹H NMR spectra also supported the proposed structures of synthesized acrylamide derivatives.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

Table 1. Physical parameters of the compounds

Compd.	Molecular formula	Color	Yield (%)	Melting point (°C)
3a	C ₉ H ₈ O ₂	White	56	132–133
6a	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ NO ₃	Off-white	65	84–85
7a	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃	Orange	75	155–157
3b	C ₉ H ₇ NO ₄	Off-white	68	196–198
6b	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₅	Off-white	67	188–189
7b	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₅	Yellow	80	252–254
3c	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ Cl	White	48	238–240
6c	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃ Cl	Yellow	62	100–102
7c	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	Off-white	74	224–227
3d	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ Cl	White	68	248–249
6d	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ NO ₃ Cl	Off-white	66	103–105
7d	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	Red	81	84–86
3e	C ₁₀ H ₉ NO ₄	White	58	195–196
6e	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₅	Yellow	70	110–112
7e	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₅	White	83	212–215
3f	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₂ Cl	White	52	136–140
6f	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ NO ₃ Cl	Yellow	69	113–115
7f	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	White	78	219–221

Antimicrobial testing :

The newly synthesized compounds viz. **6a-f** and **7a-f** were tested *in vitro* for their effect on the growth of *Rhizobium* sp. (LMR 07), *Bradyrhizobium* sp. (BJP), *Pseudomonas* sp. (LK 791) and *Bacillus* sp. (BSY 101) at 1000 µg/mL. The primary screening was carried out using the bacterial sensitivity-filter paper disc method using Congo red yeast extract mannitol agar (CRYEMA) medium for *Rhizobium* sp., *Bradyrhizobium* sp., nutrient Agar for *Bacillus* and King's B medium for *Pseudomonas* sp. Agar medium was sterilized by autoclaving at 15 psi and 121 °C for twenty minutes. The plates were prepared by pouring 15–20 mL of the sterilized media into sterilized petriplates. Plates were then allowed to solidify and stored for 2 days to ensure sterility. Suspension of 3–4 days old broth of test organism was then spread on the specific medium plates. Sterile filter paper discs moistened with test compound solution in water (2000 µg/mL) were carefully placed on the medium inoculated with the specific bacterial suspension. Sterile filter paper discs dipped in water serve as control. These plates were incubated at 28 ± 1 °C and the diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm) was measured after 24 h. The growth of the organism on medium containing the test compound was also compared

with the growth on the plates containing micro-organism without test compound that is control with unaided eye.

The results of preliminary screening of compounds (**6a-f** and **7a-f**) are shown in Tables 2 to 5. Screening results revealed that the majority of synthesized compounds showed varying degrees of inhibition against the *Rhizobium*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas*. Similar results were also reported by Kalirajan *et al.*⁸

Table 2. Microbial activity of different amides on the growth of *Rhizobium* sp. (LMR-07)

Compd.	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)				
	2000 µg/mL	1000 µg/mL	750 µg/mL	500 µg/mL	250 µg/mL
6a	9.5	8	0	0	0
7a	8	0	0	0	0
6b	11	8	7.5	7	0
7b	10	9	7	0	0
6c	12	7	0	0	0
7c	0	0	0	0	0
6d	10	8	6.5	0	0
7b	8.5	7.5	6.4	0	0
6e	13.5	11	9	8	7
7e	9	8	6.5	0	0
6f	13	11	9	7.5	0
7f	12	9	7.5	7	0
Streptomycin	14	10	9	8	0

Table 3. Microbial activity of different amides on the growth of *Bradyrhizobium* sp. (BJP)

Compd.	Diameters of growth inhibition zone (mm)				
	2000 µg/mL	1000 µg/mL	750 µg/mL	500 µg/mL	250 µg/mL
6a	15	9	7	0	0
7a	10	0	0	0	0
6b	17	15	10	8	0
7b	10	0	0	0	0
6c	16	12	9	0	0
7c	9	0	0	0	0
6d	15	11	9	0	0
7b	11	0	0	0	0
6e	24	20	18	16	13
7e	15	11	9	0	0
6f	23	18	16	13	10
7f	15	12	8	0	0
Streptomycin	28	25	22	20	17

and Al-omar⁹. Some of the amides containing morpholine moiety inhibit the growth of bacteria to large extent while amides of 4-aminophenazone showed less inhibitory effect.

The minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) for the compounds (**6a-f** and **7a-f**) showing inhibition against *Rhizobium*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* were further determined against same bacteria using micro dilution susceptibility method in respective agar medium. Stock solution of the test compounds (2000 µg/mL) was prepared in water and stored at 4 °C for further use. The stocks were diluted to 1000, 750, 500, 200, 100, 50 µg/mL. Sterile discs (high media) dipped in different concentration of test compounds were placed on the inoculated lawn of *Rhizobium* sp. (LMR 07), *Bradyrhizobium* sp. (BJP), *Bacillus* sp. (BSY 101) and *Pseudomonas* sp. (LK 791). After incubation at 28 ± 1 °C for 24 h, the MIC values were determined as the lowest concentration that inhibited visible growth of the microorganism as detected by unaided eye. The MIC of these compounds was in accordance with the results obtained in the preliminary screening (Tables 2 to 5).

So overall, the results revealed that the majority of synthesized compounds showed varying degrees of inhibition against the *Rhizobium* sp., *Bradyrhizobium* sp., *Bacillus* sp. and *Pseudomonas* sp. Maximum *Rhizobium*

Table 4. Microbial activity of different amides on the growth of *Bacillus* sp. (BSY-01)

Compd.	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)				
	2000 µg/mL	1000 µg/mL	750 µg/mL	500 µg/mL	250 µg/mL
6a	16	12	10	7	0
7a	10	7	0	0	0
6b	25	20	16	12	10
7b	12	9.3	6.4	0	0
6c	14	11	9	6.5	0
7c	9	0	0	0	0
6d	15	11	7	0	0
7b	8	7.3	6.4	0	0
6e	25	19	14	10	7
7e	21	15	11	8	0
6f	20	15	11	8	0
7f	18	12.5	9	6.5	0
Streptomycin	24	20	17	14	12

Table 5. Microbial activity of different amides on the growth of *Pseudomonas* sp. (LK-791)

Compd.	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)				
	2000 µg/ mL	1000 µg/ mL	750 µg/ mL	500 µg/ mL	250 µg/ mL
6a	11.5	10	9	7	0
7a	9	6.4	0	0	0
6b	14	12	11	10	8
7b	12	11	10	9	7
6c	12	10	9	8	0
7c	0	0	0	0	0
6d	14	13	12	10.5	8
7b	12	11	10	9	7
6e	13	10	10	8	7
7e	8	7	6.4	0	0
6f	13	12	10	8	8
7f	11	10	8.5	7	0
Streptomycin	15	14	11	10	8

sp. growth was inhibited by compounds **6e**, **6f**, **7f** and **6b**. Maximum *Bradyrhizobium* sp. growth was inhibited by compounds **6f**, **6e**, **6b** and **6c**. Maximum *Bacillus* sp. growth was inhibited by compounds **6b**, **6e**, **6c**, **6t** and **7f**. Maximum *Pseudomonas* sp. growth was inhibited by compounds **6d**, **7d**, **6b**, **7b** and **6f**. Some of the amides of morpholine showed large inhibition zone while amides of 4-aminophenazone showed moderate or very less inhibition.

Experimental

General :

All the recorded melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Structures of compounds were confirmed by routine spectrometric analysis. IR and ¹H NMR spectra were got scanned from Central Instrumentation Laboratories (CIL), Panjab University, Chandigarh. The IR spectra of compounds were recorded using KBr discs on Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer with λ_{max} in cm⁻¹ and ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance II 400 MHz instrument using TMS as an internal standard. The chemical shifts are expressed in δ (ppm) values and the abbreviations 's', 'bs', 'd', 'dd', 't' and 'm' stand for singlet, broad singlet, doublet, double doublet, triplet and multiplet respectively. The purity of compounds was checked on silica gel G coated TLC plates. The visualization of spot was carried in an iodine chamber.

General procedure for the preparation of acrylic acid :

Acetic acid (**2a**, 0.7 mol, 42.03 g) was placed in 500 mL three necked round bottom flask equipped with a reflux condenser carrying calcium chloride guard tube and NaBH₄ (0.133 mol, 5.04 g) was added slowly in small portions in flask kept in ice bath, under stirring, in order to maintain the temperature in flask below 10 °C. Then the solution obtained was stirred for 1/2 h at room temperature, and then for 1 h at 90–100 °C on oil bath. To this solution, at 70–90 °C, 0.1 mol (14.06 g) of 2-chloro benzaldehyde (**1c**) was added and then 9.91 g of *N*-methyl pyrrolidine (NMP) was added as solvent. This solution was heated under reflux, at 185–190 °C, for 10 h. The above solution was allowed to cool and was treated with 50 mL water and then with saturated sodium bicarbonate and filtered. To remove the unreactive 2-chloro benzaldehyde, the filtrate was distilled under vacuum, until the distillate was no longer cloudy. The solution was treated with HCl solution when the solid precipitates of (**3c**) were obtained in 48% yield. Absence of spot of 2-chlorobenzaldehyde on thin layer chromatographic plates revealed the purity of acid.

(E)-3-Phenylacrylic acid (**3a**) : IR (KBr) : IR bands : 3065, 3026, 2962, 1681, 1627, 1493, 1284, 942 and 767 cm⁻¹; NMR signals (δ) (DMSO-*d*₆) : 6.40 (1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz), 7.73 (1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz), 7.50–7.47 (2H, m), 7.35–7.323 (3H, m), 11.30 (1H, bs).

(E)-3-(3-Nitrophenyl)acrylic acid (**3b**) : IR bands : 3080, 1691, 1631, 1531, 1417, 1360, 1318 and 989 cm⁻¹; NMR signals (δ) (DMSO-*d*₆) : 6.2 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz), 7.22 (1H, d, *J* 16 Hz), 7.26–7.19 (1H, m), 7.57–7.54 (1H, m), 7.78–7.75 (1H, m), 7.96 (1H, s), 11.97 (1H, bs).

(E)-3-(2-Chlorophenyl)acrylic acid (**3c**) : IR bands : 1621, 3049, 983, 3001, 1686, 1305, 1422, 1470, 1686, 1887 cm⁻¹; NMR signals (δ) (DMSO-*d*₆) : 6.29 (1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz), 7.77 (1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz), 7.14–7.21 (2H, m), 7.27 (1H, dd, *J* 2.7 Hz), 7.58 (1H, dd, *J* 2.7 Hz), 12.05 (1H, bs).

(E)-3-(4-Chlorophenyl)acrylic acid (**3d**) : IR bands : 3060, 3020, 2926, 1684, 1626, 1490, 1306, 930, 821 cm⁻¹; NMR signals (δ) (DMSO-*d*₆) : 6.17 (1H, d, *J* 16.0 Hz), 7.14 (1H, d, *J* 16.0 Hz), 7.17 (2H, dd, *J* 6.4, 2.1 Hz), 7.11 (2H, dd, *J* 6.4, 1.9 Hz), 12.17 (1H, bs).

2-Methyl-3-(3-nitrophenyl)acrylic acid (3e) : *cis* and *trans* isomer were obtained in 30 : 70 ratio; IR bands : 3087, 2970, 2862, 1692, 1629, 1529, 1445, 1422, 1389, 1352, 1295, 803 cm⁻¹; NMR signals (δ) (DMSO-*d*₆) : CH₃ *cis* (Ha 0.50 (d, *J* 6.92 Hz), Hb 0.50 (d, *J* 6.92 Hz), Hc 2.02–2.19 (m)), CH₃ *trans* 1.49 (3H, s), 7.27–6.0 (1H, m, C=C-H), 7.62 (1H, s), 7.58–7.56 (1H, m), 7.18–7.12 (1H, m), 7.06–7.03 (1H, m).

2-Methyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)acrylic acid (3f) : *cis* and *trans* isomer were obtained in 20 : 80 ratio; IR bands : 3050, 1591, 3025, 834, 1917, 2933, 1674, 2859 cm⁻¹; NMR signals (δ) (DMSO-*d*₆) : CH₃ *cis* (Ha 0.69 (d, *J* 7 Hz), Hb 0.89 (d, *J* 7 Hz), Hc 2.69–2.46 (m)), CH₃ *trans* 1.89 (3H, s), 4.51–5.36 (1H, m, C=C-H), 7.3 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 7.8 (2H, d, *J* 8 Hz), 12.17 (1H, bs).

General procedure for the preparation of amide derivatives :

To a mixture of (*E*)-3-phenylacrylic acid (**3a**, 1.48 g) in dry dichloromethane (50 mL) was added thionyl chloride (1.17 g) slowly at 0 °C, then the solution was stirred at room temperature for 30 min and heated at 40 °C for 1 h. The solution was allowed to cool and the resulting solution was stirred in ice-water while morpholine (**4**, 0.86 g) was added dropwise. Triethylamine (1.01 g) was added dropwise from the dropping funnel over 15 min after the addition of morpholine. The reaction mixture was warmed to room temperature and stirred for another 2 h. The solution was partitioned between dichloromethane and 2.7 *N* HCl (50 mL) and the layers were separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with dichloromethane (50 mL). The organic layer was concentrated and diluted with saturated aqueous sodium bicarbonate and the resulting mixture is transferred to a 500 mL separatory funnel. The layers were separated, and the aqueous phase was again extracted with dichloromethane (50 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄ (anhydrous), concentrated on rotary vacuum evaporator and the crude product was recrystallized from methanol to afford 65% of amide (**6a**). The purity of compound was checked by thin layer chromatography.

(E)-1-Morpholino-3-(phenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6a**) : IR (KBr) : 1681, 1627, 1116, 1043, 2923, 2857, 1454, 702 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ CH₂ 3.54 (8H, bs), =CH 7.06 (1H, d, *J* 15.5 Hz), =CH 7.47 (1H, d, *J* 15.5 Hz), ArH 7.18–7.49 (5H, m).

(*E*)-1-Morpholino-3-(3-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6b**): IR (KBr): 1651, 1603, 1350, 1111, 1439, 742, 2923, 2858, 1531 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ CH₂ 3.66 (8H, bs), =CH 6.96 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz), =CH 7.62 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz), ArH 7.25–8.30 (4H, m).

(*E*)-1-Morpholino-3-(2-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6c**): IR (KBr): 1644, 1603, 1431, 732, 2914, 2859 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ CH₂ 3.62 (8H, bs), =CH 6.29 (1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz), =CH 7.78 (1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz), ArH 7.14–7.51 (4H, m).

(*E*)-1-Morpholino-3-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6d**): IR (KBr): 1646, 1614, 1111, 1011, 2926, 2862, 1428, 715 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ CH₂ 3.65 (8H, bs), =CH 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz), =CH 7.57 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz), ArH 7.21–7.39 (4H, m).

(*E*)-2-Methyl-1-morpholino-3-(3-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6e**): IR (KBr): 1650, 1599, 2962, 2911, 2863, 1459, 725, 1531, 844 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ CH₃ 2.02 (3H, s), CH₂ 3.59 (8H, bs), =CH 6.50 (1H, s), ArH 7.44–8.05 (4H, m).

(*E*)-2-Methyl-1-morpholino-3-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (**6f**): IR (KBr): 1626, 1115, 1031, 2968, 2922, 2858, 1459, 719, 1592 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ CH₃ 1.99 (3H, s), CH₂ 3.58 (8H, bs), =CH 6.42 (1H, s), ArH 7.14–7.33 (4H, m).

(*E*)-*N*-(1,5-Dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-3-(phenyl)acrylamide (**7a**): IR (KBr): 3193, 1655, 1542, 755, 1629 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ CH₃ 2.17 (3H, s), CH₃ 2.97 (3H, s), =C–H 6.71 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), =C–H 7.49 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz), ArH 7.18–7.49 (10H, m), NH 9.47 (s).

(*E*)-*N*-(1,5-Dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-3-(3-nitrophenyl)acrylamide (**7b**): IR (KBr): 3203, 1651, 1526, 737, 1628 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ CH₃ 2.26 (3H, s), CH₃ 3.18 (3H, s), =C–H 6.94 (1H, d, *J* 15.7 Hz), =C–H 7.53 (1H, d, *J* 15.7 Hz), ArH 7.25–8.30 (9H, m), NH 10.29 (s).

(*E*)-*N*-(1,5-Dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-3-(2-chlorophenyl)acrylamide (**7c**): IR (KBr): 3232 (N–H stretching), 1655, 757, 1626, 1538 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ CH₃ 2.19 (3H, s), CH₃ 3.06 (3H, s), =C–H 6.89 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz), =C–H 7.87

(1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz), ArH 7.14–7.51 (9H, m), NH 9.43 (s).

(*E*)-*N*-(1,5-Dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)acrylamide (**7d**): IR (KBr): 3232, 1673, 1538, 757, 1626 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ CH₃ 2.11 (3H, s), CH₃ 2.81 (3H, s), =C–H 6.46 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz), =C–H 7.37 (1H, d, *J* 15.4 Hz), ArH 7.21–7.39 (9H, m), NH 9.40 (s).

(*E*)-*N*-(1,5-Dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-2-methyl-3-(3-nitrophenyl)acrylamide (**7e**): IR (KBr): 3220, 1665, 1615, 1528, 737 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ CH₃ 2.11 (3H, s), CH₃ 2.27 (3H, s), CH₃ 3.12 (3H, s), =CH 7.27 (1H, s), ArH 7.25–7.52 (9H, m), NH 9.70 (s).

(*E*)-*N*-(1,5-Dimethyl-3-oxo-2-phenyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-2-methyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)acrylamide (**7f**): IR (KBr): 3229, 1640, 1514, 752, 1618, 2965, 2870 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ CH₃ 2.06 (3H, s), CH₃ 2.24 (3H, s), CH₃ 3.07 (3H, s), =CH 7.22 (1H, s), ArH 7.26–7.46 (9H, m), NH 9.31 (s).

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